

Original Article

Development of Cellulose Scaffolds Derived from *Ficus benjamina* Leaves for Tissue Engineering Applications

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The objective of this study was to prepare *Ficus benjamina* leaves scaffolds for tissue engineering applications. Fresh leaves were decutiniz with mixed solution of n-hexanes and diethyl ether in ratio of 9:1 and decellularized using 2.5% SDS (P1 and P2) and 5% SDS (P3 and P4) followed by incubation in 0.5% (P1, P3) and 1% (P2, P4) TnBP solution and finally soaking in 4% NaOCl for 12 to 36h. The control and decellularized leaves scaffolds samples were characterized on the basis of macroscopic observations, histological/microscopic observations, DAPI staining, DNA quantification, density and porosity, swelling property, water vapor transmission rate, FTIR spectroscopic examination, and biocompatibility assessment. Cuticular wax was completely removed by n-hexane and diethyl ether treatment and the treatment leaves were completely decellularized at 12 and 24h interval after bleaching as revealed by H&E, DAPI stained micrographs and SEM ultrastructure. DNA (ng/μl) quantity, density and of the decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaves tissue also reduced significantly (P<0.05). However, porosity, swelling percent and water vapor transmission rate of decellularized leaf scaffolds increased significantly (P<0.05). Decellularized leaf scaffolds were found hemocompatible. FTIR analysis of both control and decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaf samples showed well defined similar peaks in spectra. The subcutaneously implanted decellularized leaf scaffolds were infiltrated with host cells and found biocompatible as showed by histopathological, DAPI and SEM images. The results demonstrated that the use of SDS and TnBP by immersion technique is a suitable procedure for decellularization of *Ficus benjamina* plants leaves to produce biocompatible cellulose scaffolds.

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Introduction

Tissue engineering is a multidisciplinary field that uses the principles of engineering and life science to develop biological substitutes that create new tissues which restore, maintain or improve tissue function and potentially address significant organ/tissue shortages [1]. Autologous, artificial and animal grafts currently used for tissue replacement have limitations due to their low availability, low

biocompatibility and high cost [2]. Decellularized tissue scaffolds derived from the skin and internal organs of animals have been used for many years to improve and regenerate various tissues [3-5]. Decellularized matrix production involves different physical (freeze-thawing cycles, high hydrostatic pressure, sonication and supercritical carbon dioxide), chemical (ionic and non-ionic detergents, acid and bases, certain enzymes and Sapindus mukorossi fruit pericarp extract) and biological decellularization protocols [6-8].

Plants and animals exploit fundamentally different approaches for transporting fluids, chemicals and macro-molecules, yet there are surprising similarities in their vascular network structures. In recent years, cellulose, which is the most abundant biodegradable

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natural polymer, has been investigated intensively in the biomaterials field due to its abundant availability, no ethical issue, low cost, biocompatibility and adjustable biomechanical properties [9]. The cell wall of plants regulates cell development and proliferation similarly to the ECM of animal cells [10]. Numerous hydrogen bonds and low intermolecular attractive forces of cellulose polymers provide strength and flexible structure [11]. Cellulose-based biomaterials have been used widely in biomedical field especially for neural and cardiovascular applications as well as in bone and cartilage tissue engineering in the form of nanoparticles, fibers and their composites [9,12]. Decellularization process is confirmed by histological examination, SEM examination, DNA quantification and DAPI (4,6-diamidino-2-phenylindole 2HCl) fluorescent staining. Crapo et al. suggested that DNA content should not be >50 ng per mg of dry scaffold [6].

In the present study *Ficus benjamina* leaves were chosen for its morphological structure, which consist of two to three sub-epidermal layers and interconnected patterns which may provide a platform for the host cells to adhere and spread. The main aim was to develop a unique decellularization protocol in order to prepare cellulose matrices of *Ficus benjamina* leaves using the combination of n-hexane and diethyl ether followed by treatment with sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) and Tri-n-butyl phosphate (TnBP) in different concentrations.

Materials and Methods

Collection, decutination and decellularization of *ficus benjamina* leaves

The fresh native *Ficus benjamina* leaves were collected, cleaned (figure 1a & b) and the cuticle layer was removed by incubating the fresh leaves in the solution of 100 ml of n-hexanes: diethyl ether (figure 1c) for 10 minute as per the method described by Loneman *et al.* [13]. After washing with sterile deionized water, the leaves were decellularized using five different decellularization protocols. Briefly, the decutinated (dewaxed) leaves were transferred in the sterile plastic containers having 100ml of 2.5% (P1, P2) and 5% (P3, P4) concentrations of sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS). The samples were constantly agitated on digital orbital shaker at 120 rpm for 120 h at room temperature. Thereafter, each sample was incubated in 0.5% (P1, P3) and 1% (P2, P4) TnBP solution for 48 h. At the same time

fresh native *Ficus benjamina* leaves (C) samples were also incubated in sterile deionized water for 168 h. Decellularized leaves were washed 6 times with sterile deionized water to completely remove the traces of decellularizing agents present in the leaves. Thereafter, the samples were bleached using 4% sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) for 12 to 36 h at room temperature and washed as previously [14].

Characterization of the decellularized scaffolds

Gross macroscopic observations

After decellularization and decoloration, *Ficus benjamina* leaves samples were observed grossly for any change in colour, transparency etc. [15].

Histological/microscopic observations

Hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) staining was used to observe and detect the cellular cytoplasm and nucleus components of the native (control) and decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaves samples. For this, 10 μ m paraffin embedded sections were fixed on glass slide, cleared in Xylene-I and Xylene-II for 2 minute each, rehydrated by decreasing the ethanol concentration from 99.99% to 30%, washed with distilled water and dipped in hematoxylin for 7-8 minute. After washing, the slides were counter stained with eosin dyes for 2 minute, dehydrated by increasing the ethanol concentration, cleared in xylene and then mounted the slides. For DAPI staining, the native (control) and decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaves sections were rehydrated and then washed three times with 0.2% Tris buffered saline Tween-20 (TBST). Thereafter, the samples were stained with DAPI (Elabscience® Buffer saline solution, India) solution (200 μ l) and incubated for 10 minute in dark place at room temperature. The slides were again washed 3 times with 0.2 percent TBST and observed under a fluorescent microscope. If nuclei were detected, they fluoresced a cold blue color [16].

DNA quantification

DNA extraction and quantification of the native and decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaves scaffolds was done using cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide (C-TAB) based method [17]. The native and decellularized leaves samples were dipped in liquid nitrogen, homogenized and finally placed in sterilized centrifuge tube. Total genomic DNA was isolated from the native and decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaves scaffolds. The total amount of the DNA was quantified using spectrophotometry (NanoDrop ND1000).

Density and porosity

The density and porosity values of the native and decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaves samples of size 20 mm² were measured by liquid displacement method [18]. Briefly, the leaves samples of weight W were freeze dried for three days and immersed in a graduated cylinder containing a known volume (V_1) of ethanol. The samples were kept in the ethanol for 2 minute and then a series of brief evacuation repressurization cycles was conducted to force the ethanol into the pores of the leaves scaffolds sample. Cycling was continued until no air bubbles were observed emerging from the leaves scaffolds. The total volume of ethanol and the ethanol-impregnated leaves scaffolds was then recorded as V_2 . The volume difference ($V_2 - V_1$) was the volume of the leaves samples. The ethanol-impregnated leaves samples were removed after 2 minute from the cylinder and the residual ethanol volume recorded as V_3 . Total volume of leaves sample was:

The density (d) and porosity (%) of the native (control) and decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaves samples were calculated as per

Figure 1: Collection, cleaning of native (control) *Ficus benjamina* leaves with deionized water (a,b), removal of cuticular wax by the mixture of n-hexane and diethyl ether (c)

the given formulas

$$\text{Density} = W / (V_2 - V_3)$$

$$\text{Porosity (\%)} = (V_1 - V_3) / (V_2 - V_3) \times 100$$

Where, W - initial dry weight of leaves scaffold, V_1 - initial ethanol volume, V_2 - total volume of leaves scaffolds and ethanol, V_3 - residual ethanol volume in tube.

Swelling property/water uptake

Swelling property of native (control) and decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaves samples (n=4 each) of size 20 mm² and initial dry weight (W_o) were investigated by immersion in 1x phosphate buffered saline (PBS, pH 7.4) at room temperature. Thereafter, the weight of immersed samples was taken at an interval of 1 h, 3 h, 24 h, 72 h, 120 h and 240 h. Increase in the weight of the scaffolds were recorded and expressed as index by using equation

$$\text{Swelling (\%)} = (W_s - W_o) / W_o \times 100$$

Where, W_s = wet weight of the scaffold at a time 't' and W_o = initial weight of dry scaffold.

Water vapor transmission rate (WVTR)

Water vapor transmission rate of native (fresh) and decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaves scaffolds were performed. For this, the leaves samples were placed on plate house (37°C, humidity 35%). A certain amount of deionized water was poured into each house and the samples were incubated at a constant temperature of 37°C and relative humidity of 35%. The size of leaves samples was taken 20 x 20 mm² and the dry and wet weight of the leaves samples were measured after 24h. Water vapor transmission rate was calculated from the following formula [19].

$$\text{WVTR} = \text{mass of H}_2\text{O lost (g)} / [\text{time (day)} \times \text{area (m}^2\text{)}]$$

In vitro hemocompatibility test (red blood cells compatibility)

In vitro hemocompatibility of the native (control) and decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaves scaffolds were performed as per the method described by Rallapalli et al. [20]. In brief, fresh blood was collected from the lateral ear vein of New Zealand white rabbit in disodium EDTA vials. The blood was centrifuge at 800 rpm for 5 minutes to collect the RBCs pellet, washed with 1x PBS (pH 7.4) and centrifuged again till transparent supernatant was noted. The *Ficus*

benjamina leaves scaffold materials were immersed in the diluted RBC (1:4 ratios in PBS) and the samples were placed in incubator for one and half hours at 37°C. The fluid was collected, centrifuged for 5 minutes at 1200 rpm and absorbance was noted at 540 nm wavelength. For each specimen, the assay was carried out in triplicate, with negative and positive controls (PBS and distilled water respectively). The percentage of haemolysis was calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Hemolysis (\%)} = (A_s - A_{NC}) / (A_{PC} - A_{NC}) \times 100$$

Where A_s , A_{NC} , A_{PC} are absorbance of sample, negative control and positive control respectively.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

Scanning electron microscopic examination was performed to characterize the surface morphology of the native and decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaves scaffolds (Carl-Zeiss, EVO-18). The samples were fixed in 2.5% glutaraldehyde, transferred in serialgraded ethanol and finally submerged in HMDS for complete dehydration. The dehydrated samples were coated with a thin layer of gold-palladium at 180° (15 mA for 5 minutes). Finally, specimens were observed under SEM at 10 kV and ultramicrographs were taken from different locations [21].

Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopic analysis

Fourier transform-infrared spectroscopy of the native (control) and decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaves samples were performed using FT-IR spectrophotometer (PerkinElmer Spectrum IR version 10.7.2 model) to find out the chemical composition of the fresh and decellularized leaves samples [22]. All the spectra were recorded in the 4000 - 450 cm⁻¹ region with 32 scans in each case, at a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹.

In vivo biocompatibility analysis

The proposed protocol was approved by Institutional Animal Ethics Committee (reference no. IAEC/CVSc/P-03/2022). The natural and decellularized leaves scaffolds were implanted subcutaneously on the dorsum of the adult male New Zealand white rabbits (figure 2a-c) under xylazine hydrochloride (@ 6 mg/kg b.wt.) and ketamine hydrochloride (@ 60 mg/kg b.wt.) anesthesia [8]. The samples were retrieved on day 20 and 40 for histopathological analysis. The samples were processed and the tissue sections were stained with H&E and Masson's trichrome

Figure 2: Representative image of subcutaneous implantation of native (control) and decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaves scaffolds in New Zealand white rabbits (a,b) and skin suturing after implantation of leaf tissue (c)

Figure 3: Cuticular wax recovered after incubation of leaves in the mixture of n-hexane and diethyl ether (a), leaf after removal of cuticle (b), washing of dewaxed leaves with sterile deionized water (c)

stain using standard protocol. The ultrastructure of the biopsy samples were also analysed using SEM. The collagen fibers were categorised in thin, medium and thick on the basis of diameter and the data was analyzed using Image-J software.

Statistical analysis

The data analysis was performed using SPSS software version 18.0 (SPSS, Inc., Chicago, IL). One-way ANOVA (Analysis of variance) was used to compare the mean values of control and treatments. In addition, the Independent “t” test was used to compare the mean values between groups at different intervals.

Results

Removal of cuticle from the leaves

Mixed solution of n-hexane and diethyl ether in 9:1 ratio completely decutinized the *Ficus benjamina* leaves at 10 minutes' interval. After treatment the mixed solution of n-hexane and diethyl ether turned in to muddy- oily suspension and pellet of white foamy crystals of wax was observed at bottom of the container (figure 3a). After complete extraction of epi- and intracuticular waxes from *Ficus benjamina* leaves, no appreciable change in color of leaves was observed (figure 3b, c).

Analysis of physico-chemical properties of the decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaves scaffolds

Gross macroscopic observations

Grossly, after treatment with SDS (2.5% and 5%) followed by TnBP (0.5% and 1%) treatment, the colour of the leaves faided gradually and became brownish green at 168h in all the treatment protocols and in protocol C the colour of the leaves was not changed. At 12h, in protocols P1, P2 and P4 bleaching of chlorophyll in the leaves samples was patchy and decolourization was maximum in P1. However, in protocol P2 the leaves were completely decolorized except at central vein. In protocol C, decolourization was noted near the petiole. At 24h, in protocols P1 and P2, chlorophyll was completely removed however, in protocol P3 and P4, chlorophyll was present at the central vein. In protocol C, decolourization was noted near the petiole and at the borders only. At 36h, in protocols P3 and P4, chlorophyll was completely removed and became translucent. In protocol C, decolourization was noted near the petiole and borders of leaf (figure 4). After completion of above protocols, the leaf scaffolds samples were stored at 4°C in 1X phosphate-buffered saline(w/v) with addition of amikacine

and Amphotericin-B (25µg, Sigma-Aldrich) to prevent growth of microorganism until needed for up to two weeks. Following the decellularization process, the thickness of the leaves (n = 4) were decreased from 1305 ± 16 im to 992.56 ± 13.11 im for native (C) and decellularized leaves, respectively ($p > 0.05$).

Histological observations

The transverse section of H&E stained micrographs of native *Ficus benjamina* leaves showed uniseriate epidermis with many stomata in both adaxial and abaxial surface. The epidermis showed well developed cuticle under which double layered tightly arranged palisade parenchyma perpendicular to leaf surface was observed. Spongy parenchyma was loosely arranged. The cuticle of abaxial epidermis was thinner as compared to adaxial epidermis. Near the abaxial epidermis substomatal chamber appears as large empty cavities. The purple-blue dots spilled in the stroma represent the cell nucleus components (figure 5a). After treatment, the cuticle was completely removed from both adaxial and abaxial surface of epidermis. *Ficus benjamina* leaves were completely decellularized with minimum cell destruction. The palisade tissue was very well arranged and nucleus free. Slight destruction of stomatal cells was observed. There was no change in spongy parenchyma after treatment in all the leaves of different groups. It composed of irregular shaped parenchyma cells with large intracellular spaces. The absence of purple-blue dots and chlorophyll in the stroma of the leaves of the treatment protocols represent complete decellularization (figure 5b-e).

DAPI staining

The results of H&E stained micrographs were further confirmed by using DAPI (Elabscience) fluorescent immunostaining. The cellular and nuclear material having DNA in the native (control) *Ficus benjamina* leaf tissue showed spots of cold blue fluorescence (figure 5f). However, the leaf tissues decellularized by using the four different protocols at 168h interval showed permanent elimination of almost all nuclear components from the native leaf tissues.

DNA quantification

Quantitative evaluation of residual DNA in the *Ficus benjamina* leaf tissues decellularized using different protocols viz. P1, P2, P3 and P4 showed a significant reduction in DNA content as compared to native leaf tissues (C) (figure 6a).

Density and porosity determination

The density of native (C) and decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaf scaffold prepared using protocols P1, P2, P3 and P4 was 0.2253 ± 0.0054 , 0.0887 ± 0.0017 , 0.0813 ± 0.0023 , 0.0585 ± 0.0014 and 0.0461 ± 0.0015 g/cm³, respectively (figure 6b). However, porosity of the C, P1, P2, P3 and P4 protocols leaves / scaffolds were 16.57 ± 2.01 , 65.49 ± 0.69 , 71.37 ± 0.95 , 75.42 ± 0.63 and 78.06 ± 0.71 percent, respectively (figure 6c).

Swelling percent

The swelling (%) of *Ficus benjamina* leaves decellularized using different protocols increased significantly as compared to native (control) leaves at 1h, 3h, 24h, 72h, 120h and 240h interval (Fig 6d)

Water vapor transmission rate

The water vapor transmission rate of the native (C) *Ficus benjamina* leaves was 89.12 ± 0.213 g/day/m². However, Mean±SE of water vapor transmission rate at 24h interval in the decellularized *Ficus*

Figure 4: Gross observations of the *Ficus benjamina* leaves decellularized using 2.5% and 5% SDS followed by 0.5% and 1% TnBP and depigmented by 4% sodium hypochlorite. Leaf is dark green and opaque at zero hour, at 24h, the leaf loses some of its dark green color and begins to appear light greenish color, at 168h, the leaf is completely maintaining a brownish light hue. After being treated and sterilized with 4% sodium hypochlorite, the leaf loses its remaining color and becomes completely milky white 192-204h while in native (control) leaf milky white color is observed only at base of petiole during above time intervals.

Figure 5: H and E stained (a-e) and 4',6-Diamidino-2-phenylindole(DAPI) stained (f). (a and f) Micrograph of natural *Ficus benjamina* leaves tissue before decellularization (Control), (b-e) Decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaves tissue by protocol-P1 (b), protocol-P2 (c), protocol-P3 (d) and protocol-P4 (e and f), respectively. Cuticle, ue- upper epidermis, le-lower epidermis, pp-palisade parenchyma, sp-spongy parenchyma, st-stomatal pore, vb-vascular bundle, mp-mesophyll, nu-nucleus, cl-chlorophyll

benjamina leaf scaffolds prepared using P1, P2, P3 and P4 protocols were 287.54 ± 1.26 , 301.94 ± 1.37 , 371.29 ± 1.77 and 385.58 ± 1.23 g/day/m², respectively which was significantly ($P < 0.01$) greater than the native leaves (figure 6e).

In vitro hemocompatibility assessment

In the present study hemolysis produced by decellularised *Ficus benjamina* leaves scaffolds in P1, P2, P3 and P4 were 1.78 ± 0.05 , 1.49 ± 0.03 , 1.14 ± 0.02 and 0.70 ± 0.04 percent, respectively. However, the native *Ficus benjamina* leaves scaffolds (C) produced hemolysis by 15.38 ± 0.56 percent (figure 6f).

Scanning electron microscopic observations

The ultrastructure of native (control) leaf showed the epidermal cells, guard cells and stomata, and most of the stomatal pores were covered with cuticular wax (figure 7a, b). However, after the decellularization process the cuticular wax was completely removed and other morphological structures remained intact with disappearance of nuclear content (figure 7c, d). There was no significant change in the topographical structure of the *Ficus benjamina* leaf tissue after the decellularization process. The decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaf samples showed well-arranged vascular system with increased porosity as compared to native (control) leaf tissue.

Figure 6: Mean \pm SE of DNA content (ng/ μ l) was quantified through C-TAB method (a), Density (b) and Porosity percent (c), Swelling percent (d), WVTR (water vapor transmission rate) (e) and hemolysis percent (f) for both the control (C) and decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaves scaffolds by protocols, P1-2.5% SDS & 0.5% TnBP, P2-2.5% SDS & 1% TnBP, P3-5% SDS & 0.5% TnBP, P4- 5% SDS & 1% TnBP respectively

Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy

The fourier transform infrared spectroscopic (FTIR) analysis of native and decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaf samples was performed to compare the changes in the functional groups after processing. Both native(control) and decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaf samples showed well defined peaks at around 771, 1026, 1153, 1402, 1621, 2849, 2918 and 3397 cm^{-1} in the spectra (figure 7e, f). The peak at 3335 cm^{-1} demonstrate intra- and inter molecular hydrogen bonding of cellulose and peak at 2921 cm^{-1} represent $-\text{CH}_2$ anti-symmetrical stretching of wax substances with some contribution from other macromolecules such as carbohydrates. The bands around 1700 - 1740 cm^{-1} corresponds to the $\text{C}=\text{O}$ stretch of xylan in hemicelluloses, esters or the functional groups in lignin's structure. The band at 1614 cm^{-1} demonstrate aromatic $\text{C}=\text{C}$ stretch and/or asymmetric $\text{C}-\text{O}$ stretch in COO^- of lignin or asymmetric COO^- of pectin. The peak at 1422 cm^{-1} demonstrated CH_2 scissoring of cellulose and also of hemicellulose, lignin and pectin. The peak at 1149 cm^{-1} demonstrate $\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{C}$ stretching of non-cellulosic materials such as hemicellulose and pectin and at 1095 cm^{-1} anti-symmetric in-plane stretching of $\text{C}-\text{C}$ was observed as well. The absorbance peak at 1019 cm^{-1} represents $\text{C}-\text{O}$ stretch of cellulose, hemicellulose, and pectin.

Gross macroscopic observations

Throughout the study, there were no symptoms of visible inflammation or infection at the implantation site. On day 20 healthy tissues was observed surrounding the *Ficus benjamina* leaf scaffold with the presence of blood vessels that are proximal or in direct contact and the scaffolds retain their square shape. On day 40 most of the healthy tissue was observed which surrounded the cellulose scaffold with the presence of blood vessels that are in direct contact. The rest of the leaf scaffolds were absorbed by host tissue indicating the better biocompatibility (figure 8a, b). The retrieved implants with surrounding subcutaneous tissue were evaluated by histopathology, DAPI and SEM examinations.

Histopathological examinations

Native *Ficus benjamina* leaves implanted rabbits at day 20 the H&E stained sections showed encapsulation of the subcutaneously implanted native leaf tissue which displays the symptoms of moderate to severe immune response and inflammatory reaction with accumulation of inflammatory cells. Little bit adherence of some pink color cytoplasmic material was also observed on the native leaf tissue (figure 9a). Dense infiltration of the inflammatory cells like granulocytes can be clearly seen within the native *Ficus benjamina* leaves tissue. Polymorphonuclear (PMNs) cells population

Figure 7: Scanning Electron Microscope image of surface topography for both of control (a,b) and decellularized (c,d) *F. benjamina* leaves scaffolds at the end of study with three different magnifications 100X (a and c) and 1500X(b and d), which confirmed decellularization process of the scaffolds by showing removal of cuticle. White arrow-cuticular wax, Black line- stomatal area. Fouriertransform infrared (FTIR) analysis of the control (e) and decellularized (f) *Ficus benjamina* leaves scaffolds were demonstrated by using the sessile water drop

Figure 8: Gross observation of subcutaneously implanted *Ficus benjamina* leaves scaffolds collected at day 20 (a) and at day 40(b) in New Zealand white rabbits

of the granulocyte within the native leaf tissue was dominant. Both axial and abaxial epidermis, palisade parenchyma spongy parenchyma, chlorophyll and mesophyll of the leaf were clearly visible. Dead cells and cell debris were also observed within the stroma. These findings clearly showed acute foreign body reaction against the native *Ficus benjamina* leaves tissue (figure 9a). On day 20, the surface of the decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaves implanted tissue was infiltrated with host tissue accumulation and neovascularization but inner leaf tissue was intact (figure 9b). On day 40 the surface of the native leaf was infiltrated with host tissue only at mid part and some dead cells and cell debris was also observed within the stroma (figure 9c). However, in decellularized leaf scaffold the cell population was migrated into the scaffolds and some epidermal cells of leaf were observed and rest of the leaf scaffolds were absorbed by host tissue indicating the better biocompatibility (figure 9d). Masson's trichrome stained native leaf tissue, showed dead cells and cell debris within the stroma. These findings clearly showed acute foreign body reaction against the native *Ficus benjamina* leaves tissue. Penetration of collagen fibers in both axial and abaxial epidermis, palisade parenchyma spongy

Figure 9: Hematoxylin-eosin (H & E), Masson’s trichrome (MTS) and 4’,6-Diamidino-2-phenylindole(DAPI) stained micrographs of the subcutaneously implanted control (a,c,e,g,i,k) and decellularized (b,d,f,h,j,l) *Ficus benjamina* leaves tissue collected at day 20 and day 40 of following implantation, respectively. (bf– Blue Fluorescent, bv-Blood vessels, cd-cell debris, ep– Epidermis, mp-Mesophyll, nc-New collagen, pp-Palisade parenchyma, vb– Vascular bundle)

Figure 10: Scanning electron microscope images from control (a and c) and decellularized (b and d) *F. benjamina* leaves tissue retrieve at day 20 (a and b) and day 40 (c and d) of following subcutaneously implantation in New Zealand white rabbits respectively

parenchyma, chlorophyll and mesophyll tissue of the leaf, was clearly visible (figure 9e). At day 20, in the decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaves implanted tissue, the surface of the leaf was infiltrated with host tissue including collagen fibers accumulation and neovascularization (figure 9f). On day 40 the surface of the native leaf was infiltrated with host tissue only at mid part with huge deposition of blue color collagen fiber around the leaf tissue. Some dead cells and cell debris were also observed within the stroma (figure 9g). However, in decellularized leaf scaffolds the cell population was migrated into the scaffolds and most part of the leaf scaffold was replaced by blue color collagen fiber (figure 9h).

In vivo biocompatibility and cell infiltration was examined with DAPI (4, 6-diamidino-2-phenylindole 2HCl) stained the cellular and nuclear material having DNA of native (control) and decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaf scaffolds at day 20 and 40 following their subcutaneous implantation represent spots of cold blue fluorescence. The cross section of representative image of native and decellularized leaves scaffolds are shown in figure 9i-l. Decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaf was used for *in vivo* biocompatibility test. On day 20 the tissues collected from the native *Ficus benjamina* leaves implanted rabbits showed the spots of cold blue fluorescence at corner (margin) of cell walls and some at center of cells (figure 9i). At day 20, in the decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaves implanted tissue, the surface of the leaf showed the spots of cold blue fluorescence at margin of cell walls as well as center of cells was observed (figure 9j). On day 40 the surface of the native leaf was infiltrated with host tissue only at mid part with deposition of spots of cold blue fluorescence (figure 9k). However, in decellularized leaf scaffolds showed a complete difference in both the surrounding tissue and spots of cold blue fluorescence were observed. The subcutaneous tissue surrounding the leaves scaffold has more population of within the surrounding scaffolds now contain higher levels of cellular and nuclear material having DNA in and around (figure 9l).

Scanning electron microscopic examination

The SEM images of native and decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaves scaffolds at day 20 and 40 are presented in figure 10a-d. In the tissues collected at day 20 the SEM images showed that the subcutaneous tissue surrounding native (control) leaf displays overall extensive depositions of unorganized wavy collagen fibers. The stroma showed disintegrated leaf parts and debris. Collagen fibers in low density with some cross-linking were observed (figure 10a). At day 20, in the decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaves implanted tissue the surfaces were covered with a glossy material, indicating the development of new regenerated organized parallel arranged collagen fibers. The decellularized scaffold was completely absorbed and no part of the scaffold was visible at this time interval. The pores of the underlying graft were filled with stroma and growth of fibroblasts into scaffolds matrix at host graft junction was observed (figure 10b). On day 40 the surface of the native leaf was infiltrated with host tissue and some rounded cells were found mostly on the top surfaces with the highest density. This was probably also the reason their outer surfaces appeared irregular. They were relatively sparse within the tissue but often formed bigger, tighter groups. They usually appeared large and round, but sometimes they were oval or spindle shaped (figure 10c). However, in decellularized leaf scaffolds the SEM images showed an overall surface were covered with a significant amount of a glossy material, indicating the development of new regenerated collagen fibers and dense collagen fibrous meshwork. Fibroblasts were infiltrated within the pores of scaffolds. The growth of cells was found mostly on the top surfaces of scaffolds with the highest density in aligned

direction on the collagen fibers. They usually appeared large and round, but sometimes they were oval or spindle shaped (figure 10d).

Discussion

The cellulose is the most abundant biodegradable natural polymer that is easily accessible in nature is new in the biomaterials field due to its availability, no ethical issue, low cost, biocompatibility and adjustable biomechanical properties. In the present study, the *Ficus benjamina* leaves were decellularized using mixture of n-hexane and diethyl ether in 9:1 ratio and decellularized using 2.5% and 5% concentrations of SDS under continuous agitation at 180rpm at room temperature for 120h followed by 0.5% and 1% TnBP treatment for 48h. The decellularized leaves scaffolds were characterized by observing the scaffolds physico-chemical properties and *in vitro* and *in vivo* biocompatibility.

The cuticle wax is super-long chain fatty acids and their derivatives hydrophobic compounds such as alkanes, primary alcohols and ketones which covers the surface of terrestrial plants and prevents the water loss invasion of pathogens. It is necessary to remove the cuticle layer so that the decellularizing agent can easily penetrate the leaf tissue uniformly. The cuticle can be extracted using organic solvents such as chloroform, methanol, dichloro-methane, n-hexane, petroleum ether, or toluene [15]. However, we found that n-hexane alone did not completely extract the epi- and intracuticular waxes, probably due to their more hydrophobicity of the cuticle. Thus, mixture of n-hexane and diethyl ether in 9:1 ratio was used to remove the cuticle in our procedure because it penetrated easily and extracted the complete epi- and intracuticular waxes. Cuticle layer from the leaf's surface can be removed using hexanes and 1X phosphat buffered saline (PBS) [22,23] and dulbecco's phosphate-buffered saline (DPBS) and hexanes [24].

Each leaf was immersed in the separate container and decellularized using SDS followed by TnBP treatment under continuous shaking. The detergent-based decellularization process was also adopted on plant leaves [11,14,16]. In the present study SDS was selected for decellularization of *F. benjamina* leaves because it solubilizes cell membranes and effectively removes the nuclear materials in shorter time frames compared to other chemical treatments [25]. Zwitterionic detergents such as tri-n-butyl phosphate (TnBP) preserves the extracellular matrix (ECM) [26] and capable of successful removal of DNA content from the ECM membrane when used in tandem with chemical decellularizing agents. Various researchers used perfusion-based technique for decellularization of leaf and cellulose scaffold [15,23,27]. Decellularization is made easier by the porosity nature of most plants, which enables quick interchange of detergents, buffers and media without the need for a perfusion system. Therefore, using simply detergent, the decellularized cellulose scaffold may be produced efficiently [28,29]. Avoid processing of more than one leaves in a container at a time because it may cause an inconsistent decellularization.

At 24h, in protocols P1 and P2, and at 36h in protocols P3 and P4, the chlorophyll was completely removed and the leaves were completely decolorized and became translucent. In protocol C, decolorization was noted only near the petiole and borders of leaf at this time interval. The plant leaves turned transparent white at 36h after decellularization and bleaching with 10% SDS and 10% sodium hypochlorite, respectively. For the leaf to become transparent

it may take time from one day to several weeks, depending on the leaf's qualities (e.g., size, thickness, lobing and chemistry). The green plant leaf turned transparent white after treatment with SDS (10%) followed by 0.1% triton-x-100 in a sodium hypochlorite bleach for 5 days using perfusion technique [15].

In all four treatment protocols, absence of nucleus and chlorophyll in the stroma of the leaves represent complete decellularization. In H & E stained micrographs of native leaves tissues, nuclei were observed but they were abolished from the decellularized leaves [15,29]. Elimination of almost all DNA from the cells of the processed tissue is a crucial part in decellularization process. *Ficus benjamina* leaf tissue decellularized using four different treatment protocol leads to significant elimination of cellular and nuclear material as shown in the DAPI stained leaf tissues.

Significant ($P < 0.05$) drop in DNA concentration from 111.28 ± 2.08 (Control) to 14.26 ± 0.54 ng/ μ l (P4) was noted which clearly indicated elimination of plant cell material following decellularization [15,22,27,30,31]. This result is below the generally acknowledged criterion of $d^{*}50$ ng/mg for suitably decellularized tissue [6]. Furthermore, when measuring DNA content from native vegetal material, the presence of a significant microbial population that is present in plants might be seen and cause an overestimation [32].

The density of scaffolds plays a vital role in tissue engineering and essential for cell recruitment, tissue growth and function [33,34]. The decreased in density of decellularized leaf through protocol (P4) in compare to native (control) tissue might be due to loss of cellular material and creation of pore during decellularization. The structural properties of the scaffolds e.g. porosity and pore size have direct implications on their functionality both *in vitro* and *in vivo*. Poor porosity and smaller size pores represent a few of the obstacles to cell adhesion, proliferation and migration [35]. A high level of porosity is typically required to produce a homogeneous distribution of cells across the intended tissue matrix. Cell dispersion, infiltration, and adhesion are facilitated by macropores bigger than 100 nm [36]. Decellularized spinach leaves can sustain numerous mammalian cell types as a vascularized scaffold [11,15]. The biomechanical properties of scaffolds are significantly impacted by a higher porosity [37]. Soft tissues, such as leaves, the structure becomes slack due to the long period of oscillation and washing during the decellularization process, resulting in the large increase of pore size. After decellularization, the changes of pore size of different types of plants are different, which may be related to the mechanical strength of plants [38].

The ability of scaffolds to absorb water is crucial for tissue engineering [39]. Since better nutrition delivery and cell growth and proliferation within the scaffolds are related to the scaffolds' potential to absorb water, hydration assessment was conducted to ascertain the capacity to absorb water. The increase in swelling percent of decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaves may be the result of their porous structure and increased hydrophilicity. The loss of cellular material during the decellularization process enhanced the liquid adsorption efficiency, which resulted in a rise in the swelling ratio of the decellularized specimens.

The vapor permeability of decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaf tissue was higher ($P < 0.05$) which might be due to loss of series of control barriers such as stomatal protective cells in the entry and exit of

material and creation of pore during decellularization and porosity increases the vapor permeability of scaffolds [21]. The rate of water vapor transmission has been reported to be 218 g/ m^2 for dry human skin and 350 g/ m^2 for wet skin [40]. WVTR for hydrocolloid dressings such as granuflex and comfeel, was about 216 g/day/ m^2 and 285g/day/ m^2 , respectively [41].

The hemolysis analysis was used in this study to rule out the presence of any nuclear or cellular material within the decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaf matrices since biocompatibility assessment is essential for every biomaterial to be implanted in the body. Among the most crucial aspect in determining biocompatibility is the degree of erythrocyte rupture generated by any implant [42]. The amount of hemolysis brought on by the decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaves scaffolds was significantly ($P < 0.05$) less than the permitted limit. It might be due to loss of cuticular wax, cytoplasmic and nuclear content during process of decellularization. It is implied that the matrices are not biocompatible for *in vivo* grafting if there is a greater degree of RBCs rupture brought on by the biomaterial that might result in graft failure. Implants shouldn't induce greater than 2% hemolysis, whether they are synthetic or biological [43]. Hemolysis may also be increased by a rise in surface granularity or the presence of trichomes on the exterior of the leaf.

The ultrastructures of decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaf tissue showed significantly increased stomatal pore length, stomatal pore width and stomatal pore area which might be due to removal of cuticle, cellular content and barriers such as stomatal protective cells during process of decellularization. After decellularization, the scaffold becomes more porous [11]. The epidermis of the leaf was intact and the nuclei were absent and the pore size of the decellularized leaf tissue was larger than the pore size of native leaf tissue. The topographical architecture of the leaf specimens did not alter significantly following the decellularization technique [44].

FTIR spectroscopy was used to compare the functional groups arising from macromolecules associated with cellulose, hemicellulose, lignin, pectin, and wax substances present in native and decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaves. The C-H deformation bond in cellulose and hemicellulose was proven by 894 cm^{-1} peak which represents the cellulose content in the decellularized scaffolds. The spectra featured a most typical band at 2918 cm^{-1} to 2922 cm^{-1} corresponded to the C-H stretching vibrations [45]. The peak observed in both native and decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaf at about 1734 cm^{-1} which revealed C=O stretch of hemicelluloses. The bands between 1700 and 1740 cm^{-1} could be the functional groups in lignin's architecture or the C=O stretch of xylan seen in hemicelluloses [46]. Transmittance peak at 1629 cm^{-1} indicate aromatic C=C stretch and/or asymmetric C-O stretch in COO- of lignin or asymmetric COO- of pectin [47]. Decrease in the peak's strength indicates that the greatest amount of lignin and pectin has been removed by chemical extraction which was noted at 1620 cm^{-1} in native *Ficus benjamina* leaf and at 1622 cm^{-1} in the decellularized leaf. The aromatic C=C ring stretching and C-H deformation in the methyl, methylene and methoxyl groups of lignin are shown by the bands at 1505 cm^{-1} and 1458 cm^{-1} in the fiber [47,48] and in present study these peaks were shifted at 1543 cm^{-1} and 1402 cm^{-1} in both native and decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaf tissue. The transmittance peak at 1318 cm^{-1} shows CH_2 rocking vibration of cellulose [49]. The peak observed in the both native and decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaf at 1153 cm^{-1} reveals C-O-C

stretching of non-cellulosic materials such as hemicellulose and pectin. The C-O anti-symmetrical bridge stretching and the in-plane ring stretching are depicted by transmittance peak at 1157 cm^{-1} [50]. The peak at 1092 cm^{-1} revealed C-O and C-C stretch [44] which was noted at 1063 cm^{-1} in native leaf and at 1066 cm^{-1} in the decellularized leaf.

The decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaves implanted tissue was infiltrated with host tissue including collagen fibers accumulation and neovascularization within the void spaces of the scaffold. Vegetable cellulose scaffolds must have minimal immunogenicity and better biocompatibility with the animal host in order to be employed as tissue grafts [51]. By eight weeks after implantation, the immunological reaction gradually decreased and the cellulose scaffold was showing signs of active fibroblast movement [27]. Decellularized apple tissue scaffold induced a mild inflammatory reaction and even promoted angiogenesis and ECM buildup [52]. On day 40 the cell population was migrated into the scaffolds and some epidermal cells of leaf were observed and rest of the leaf scaffolds were absorbed and replaced by host tissue indicating the better biodegradability and biocompatibility of plant cellulose in vivo [27]. Mammalian cells adhered, survived and multiplied on grafted leaf scaffolds without any negative immunological reaction [14,27,52]. The cell infiltration within the decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaf scaffolds at day 20th and 40th following their subcutaneously implantation was also confirmed by cold blue fluorescence observed in DAPI (4, 6-diamidino-2-phenylindole 2HCl) stained tissue.

The ultrastructure of subcutaneously implanted *Ficus benjamina* leaf scaffolds collected at day 20 and 40 demonstrated a series of nanofibrous structures. Many of the nanofibers appeared to assemble and form larger micro-scale fibrils within the retrieved tissue. Plant based cellulose scaffold attaches the host cells in to the structure, with their morphologies varying between round and spread, consistent with other mammalian cells grown in other natural and synthetic 3D scaffolds [53]. Increased diameter of collagen fibers in decellularized leaf scaffolds implanted tissue as compared to native leaf tissue might be due to early penetration and maturation of collagen fibers in decellularized leaf scaffold. The pore diameter (nm) of collagen matrix in decellularized leaf scaffold implanted tissue was significantly decreased ($P < 0.05$) which might be due to more growth of subcutaneous tissue in decellularized leaf scaffolds.

The biopsy sample collected at day 20 showed severe inflammatory reaction with accumulation of inflammatory cells around the leaf with encapsulation of the native leaf tissue. However, the decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaves implanted tissue was infiltrated with host tissue including collagen fibers accumulation and neovascularization within the void spaces of the scaffold. Vegetable cellulose scaffolds must have minimal immunogenicity and better biocompatibility with the animal host in order to be employed as tissue grafts [51]. By eight weeks after implantation, the immunological reaction gradually decreased and the cellulose scaffold was showing signs of active fibroblast movement [27]. Decellularized apple tissue scaffold were implanted subcutaneously in mice and it mildly induced an inflammatory reaction and even promoted angiogenesis and ECM buildup [52]. On day 40 the surface of the native leaf was infiltrated with inflammatory cells only at mid part. However, in decellularized leaf scaffolds the cell

population was migrated into the scaffolds and some epidermal cells of leaf were observed and rest of the leaf scaffolds were absorbed and replaced by host tissue indicating the better biocompatibility. Mammalian cells adhered, survived and multiplied on grafted leaf scaffolds [15,52]. The cellulose-based decellularized apple hypanthium tissue also showed good biocompatibility and biodegradability of plant cellulose *in vivo* [27]. Similarly, when decellularized leaves were implanted in rats, there was no negative immunological reaction [14]. The infiltration of fibroblasts and other cells within the decellularized *Ficus benjamina* leaf scaffolds at day 20th and 40th following their subcutaneously implantation was confirmed by cold blue fluorescence observed in DAPI (4, 6-diamidino-2-phenylindole 2HCl) stained tissue.

In decellularized leaf scaffolds the SEM images showed an overall surface were covered with a significant amount of a glossy material, indicating the development of new regenerated collagen fibers and dense collagen fibrous meshwork. Fibroblasts were infiltrated within the pores of scaffolds. The growth of cells was found mostly on the top surfaces of scaffolds with the highest density in aligned direction on the collagen fibers. They usually appeared large and round, but sometimes they were oval or spindle shaped. This was probably also the reason their outer surfaces appeared irregular [53]. Plant based cellulose scaffold attaches the host cells in to the structure, with their morphologies varying between round and spread, consistent with other mammalian cells grown in other natural and synthetic 3D scaffolds [54].

Conclusion

The results demonstrated that the use of SDS and TnBP by immersion technique is a suitable procedure for decellularization of *Ficus benjamina* plants leaves to produce cellulose scaffolds. Moreover, the leaves scaffolds can easily be prepared into specific shapes and sizes, offering an opportunity to create new tissues with specific geometrical properties. The leaves derived biomaterials offer potential approach for the production of implantable scaffolds. Plant derived materials are cost effective, biocompatible, promotes the vascularization and might be considered as a new strategy for tissue regeneration in tissue engineering applications.

References

1. Vacanti, J., Tissue engineering and regenerative medicine: from first principles to state of the art. *Journal of Pediatric Surgery*, 45 (2), 291-294 (2010).
2. Mason, C., Dunnill, P., A brief definition of regenerative medicine. *Future Medicine*, 3(1), 1-5 (2008).
3. Gangwar, A.K., Sharma, A.K., Kumar, N., Kumar, N., Maiti, S. K., Gupta, O.P., Singh, R., Acellular dermal graft for repair of abdominal wall defects in rabbits. *Journal of the South African Veterinary Association*, 77(2), 79-85 (2006).
4. Goyal, R.P., Gangwar, A.K., Khangembam, S.D., Yadav, V.K., Kumar, R., Verma, R.K., Kumar, N., Decellularization of caprine esophagus using fruit pericarp extract of *Sapindus mukorossi*. *Cell and Tissue Banking*, 23, 1-14 (2021).
5. Kumar, V., Gangwar, A.K., Kumar, N., Singh, H., Use of the buhaline acellular diaphragm matrix for umbilical hernioplasty in pigs. *Veterinarski Arhiv*, 85, 49-58 (2015).
6. Crapo, P.M., Gilbert, T.W., Badylak, S.F., An overview of tissue and whole organ decellularization processes. *Biomaterials*, 32(12), 3233-3243 (2011).
7. Gangwar, A.K., Naveen Kumar, Devi K.S., Kumar, V. and Singh, R., Primary chicken embryo fibroblasts seeded acellular dermal matrix (3-D ADM) improve regeneration of full thickness skin wounds in rats. *Tissue and Cell*, 47, 311-322 (2015).
8. Goyal, R.P., Khangembam, S.D., Gangwar, A.K., Development of

- decellularized aortic scaffold for regenerative medicine using Sapindus mukorossi fruit pericarp extract. *Micron* 142, 102997 (2022).
9. Jorfi, M., Foster, E.J., Recent advances in nanocellulose for biomedical applications. *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, 132(14), 1 (2015).
 10. Lodish, H., Berk, A., Zipursky, S. L., *Molecular Cell Biology*, 4th edn. New York: WH Freeman (2000).
 11. Fontana, G., Gershlak, J., Adamski, M., Lee, J., Matsumoto, S., Le, H.D., Binder, B., Wirth, J., Gaudette, G., Murphy, W.L., Biofunctionalized plants as diverse biomaterials for human cell culture. *Advanced Healthcare Materials*, 6, 1601225 (2017).
 12. Namvar, F., Jawaid, M., Tanir, P. M., Mohamad, R., Azizi, S., Khodavandi, A., Nayeri, M.D., Potential use of plant fibres and their composites for biomedical applications. *BioResources*, 9(3), 5688-5706 (2014).
 13. Loneman, D.M., Peddicord, L., Al-Rashid, A., Nikolau, B. J., Lauter, N., Yandeau-Nelson, M. D. A robust and efficient method for the extraction of plant extracellular surface lipids as applied to the analysis of silks and seedling leaves of maize. *PLoS ONE*, 12(7), 1-21 (2017).
 14. Adamski, M., Fontana, G., Gershlak, J., Gaudette, G., Le, H.D., Murphy, W.L., Two methods for decellularization of plant tissues for tissue engineering applications, *Journal of Visualized Experiments*, 135, 1-7 (2018).
 15. Gershlak, J.R., Hernandez, S., Fontana, G., Perreault, L.R., Hansen, K.J., Larson, S.A., Gaudette, G.R., Crossing kingdoms: Using decellularized plants as perfusable tissue engineering scaffolds. *Biomaterials*, 125, 13-22 (2017).
 16. Salehi, A., Amin Mobarhan, M., Mohammadi, J., Shahsavarani, H., Ali Shokrgozar, M., Alipour, A., Efficient mineralization and osteogenic gene overexpression of mesenchymal stem cells on Decellularized spinach leaf scaffold, *Gene*. 757(5), 144852 (2020a)
 17. Querci, M., Kagkli, D.M., Gatto, F., Foti, N., Maretta, M., Mazzara, M., The analysis of food samples for the presence of Genetically Modified Organisms User Manual, EUR, 30145EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, (2020).
 18. Hsu, Y.Y., Gresser J. D., Trantolo, D. J., Lyons, C.M., Gangadharam, P.R., Wise, D.L., Effect of polymer foam morphology and density on kinetics of in vitro controlled release of isoniazid from compressed foam matrices. *Journal Biomedical Materials Research*, 35(1), 107-116 (1997).
 19. Hu, Y., Topolkarav, V., Hiltner, A., Baer, E., Measurement of water vapor transmission rate in highly permeable films. *Journal of applied polymer science*, 81(7), 1624-1633 (2001).
 20. Rallapalli, S., Liman, A.M., Guhathakurta, S., Hemocompatibility and surface properties of bovine pericardial patches: Effects of gamma sterilization. *Current Medicine Research and Practice*, 6,224-228 (2016).
 21. Salehani, A.A., Rabbani, M., Biazar, E., Heidari Keshel, S., Pourjabbar, B., The effect of chemical detergents on the decellularization process of olive leaves for tissue engineering applications. *Engineering Reports*, e12560 (2022).
 22. Salehi, A., Mobarhan, M. A., Mohammadi, J., Shahsavarani, H., Shokrgozar, M. A., Alipour, A., Cabbage-derived three-dimensional cellulose scaffold induced osteogenic differentiation of stem cells. *Journal of Cell Physiology*, 236, 5306-5316 (2020).
 23. Robbins, E.R., Pins, G.D., Laflamme, M.A., Gaudette, G.R., Creation of a contractile biomaterial from a decellularized spinach leaf without ECM protein coating: an in vitro study. *Journal of Biomedical Materials Research, Part A*. 108, 2123-2132 (2020).
 24. Wang, Y., Dominko, T., Weathers, P.J., Using decellularized grafted leaves as tissue engineering scaffolds for mammalian cells. *In vitro Cellular and Developmental Biology-Plant*. 56, 765-774 (2020).
 25. Gangwar, A.K., Kumar, N., Khangembam, S.D., Kumar, V., Singh, R., Primary chicken embryo fibroblasts seeded acellular dermal matrix (3-D ADM) improve regeneration of full thickness skin wounds in rats. *Tissue and Cell*, 47(3), 311-322 (2015).
 26. Mendibil, U., Ruiz-Hernandez, R., Retegi-Carrion, S., Tissue-specific decellularization methods: Rationale and strategies to achieve regenerative compounds. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 21:5447 (2020).
 27. Modulevsky, D.J., Cuerrier, C.M., Pelling, A.E., Biocompatibility of Subcutaneously Implanted Plant-Derived Cellulose Biomaterials. *PLoS One*, 21, 11(6) (2016).
 28. Zhu, Y., Zhang, Q., Wang, S., Zhang, J., Fan, S., Lin, X., Current Advances in the Development of Decellularized Plant Extracellular Matrix. *Frontiers in Bioengineering*, 9, 712262 (2021).
 29. Thippam, M., Dhoolappa, M., Lakshishree, K.T., Sheela, P., Prasad, R., Morphology of medicinal plant leaves for their functional vascularity. A novel approach for tissue engineering applications. *International Journal of Chemical Studies*, 7(3), 55-58 (2019).
 30. Piccoli, M., Urbani, L., Alvarez-Fallas, M.E., Franzin, C., Dedja, A., Bertin, E., Pozzobon, M., Improvement of diaphragmatic performance through orthotopic application of decellularized extracellular matrix patch. *Biomaterials*, 74, 245-255 (2016).
 31. Dikici, S., Claeysens, F., MacNeil, S., Decellularised Baby Spinach Leaves and their Potential Use in Tissue Engineering Applications. *Journal of Biomaterials Applications*, 34, 546-559 (2019).
 32. Harris, A.F., Lacombe, J., Zenhausern, F., The Emerging Role of Decellularized Plant-Based Scaffolds as a New Biomaterial. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 22, 12347 (2021b).
 33. Bullington, L.S., Lekberg, Y., Larkin, B.G., Insufficient Sampling Constrains Our Characterization of Plant Microbiomes. *Science Reporter*, 11, 3645 (2021).
 34. Annabi, N., Nichol, J.W., Zhong, X. Ji. C., Koshy, S., Khademhosseini, A., Dehghani, F., Controlling the porosity and micro architecture of hydrogels for tissue engineering. *Tissue Engineering Part B*, 16(4), 371-83(2010).
 35. Loh, Q.L., Choong, C., Three-dimensional scaffolds for tissue engineering applications: Role of porosity and pore size. *Tissue Eng Part B Rev*, 19(6), 485-502 (2013).
 36. Dong, X., Wei, X., Yi, W., Gu, C., Kang, X., Liu, Y., RGD-modified acellular bovine pericardium as a bioprosthetic scaffold for tissue engineering. *Journal of Materials Science Materials in Medicine*, 20, 2327-36 (2009).
 37. Vagaska, B., Bacakova, L., Filovaa, E., Balik, K., Osteogenic cells on bio-inspired materials for bone tissue engineering. *Physiological Research*, 59(3), 309-322 (2010).
 38. Luo, Z., Yang, Y., Deng, Y., Sun, Y., Yang, H., Wei, S., Peptide-incorporated 3D porous alginate scaffolds with enhanced osteogenesis for bone tissue engineering. *Colloids and Surfaces B: Biointerfaces*, 143, 243-251(2016).
 39. Lee, J., Jung, H., Park, N., Park, S.H., Ju, J.H., Induced osteogenesis in plants decellularized scaffolds. *Scientific Reports*, 9(1), 1-10 (2019).
 40. Agarwal, T., Narayan, R., Maji, S., Behera, S., Kulanthavel, S., T.K. Maiti, T. K., Banerjee, I., Pal, K., Giri, S., Gelatin/Carboxymethyl chitosan based scaffolds for dermal tissue engineering applications. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules*, 93, 1499-1506 (2016).
 41. Ruiz-Cardona, L., Sanzgeri, Y.D., Benedetto, L.M., Stella, V.J., Topp, E.M., Application of benzyl hyaluronate membranes as potential wound dressings: evaluation of water vapor and gas permeabilities. *Biomaterials*, 17(16), 1639-1643(1996).
 42. Wu, P., Fisher, A.C., Foo, P.P., Queen, D., Gaylor, J.D., In vitro assessment of water vapor transmission of synthetic wound dressings. *Biomaterials*, 16(3), 171-175 (1995).
 43. Gao, Y., Chen, L., Zhang, Z., Gu, W., Li, Y., Linear cationic click polymer for gene delivery: Synthesis, biocompatibility, and in vitro transfection. *Biomacromolecules*. 11(11), 3102-3111(2010).
 44. Liu, Y., Cai, D., Yang, J., Wang, Y., Zhang, X., Yin, S., In vitro hemocompatibility evaluation of poly (4-hydroxybutyrate) scaffold. *International Journal of Clinical and Experimental Medicine*, 7(5), 1233 (2014).
 45. Toker, M., Rostami, S., Kesici, M., Decellularization and characterization of leek: a potential cellulose-based biomaterial. *Cellulose*, 27, 7331-7348 (2020).
 46. Kathirselvam, M., Kumaravel, A., Arthanarieswaran, V.P., Saravanakumar, S.S., Assessment of cellulose in bark fibers of *Thespesia populnea*: Influence of stem maturity on fiber characterization. *Carbohydrate Polymers*, 212, 439-449 (2019).
 47. Bergs, M., Volkering, G., Kraska, T., Pude, R., Do, X.T., Kusch, P., Monakhova, Y., Konow, C., Schulze, M., Miscanthus x giganteus Stem Versus Leaf-Derived Lignins Differing in Monolignol Ratio and Linkage. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 20(5), 1200 (2019).
 48. Sain, M., Panthapulakkal, S., Bioprocess preparation of wheat straw fibers and their characterization. *Industrial Crops and Products*, 23(1), 1-8 (2006).
 49. Maheswari, U.C., Obi Reddy, K., Muzenda, E., Guduri, B.R., Varada Rajulu, A., Extraction and characterization of cellulose microfibrils from agricultural residue-Cocos nucifera L. *Biomass and Bioenergy*, 46, 555-563 (2012).
 50. Schwanninger, M., Rodrigues, J. C., Pereira, H., Hinterstoisser, B., Effects of short-time vibratory ball milling on the shape of FT-IR spectra of wood and cellulose. *Vibrational Spectroscopy*, 36(1), 23-40 (2004).

51. Abidi, N., Cabrales, L., Haigler, Changes in the cell wall and cellulose content of developing cotton fibers investigated by FTIR spectroscopy. *Carbohydrate Polymers*, 100, 9-16 (2014).
52. Helenius, G., Backdahl, H., Bodin, A., Nannmark, U., Gatenholm, P., Risberg, B., In vivo biocompatibility of bacterial cellulose. *Journal Biomedical Materials Research Part A*. 76A, 431–438 (2006).
53. Modulevsky, D. J., Lefebvre, C., Haase, K., Al-Rekabi, Z., Pelling, A.E., Apple derived cellulose scaffolds for 3D mammalian cell culture. *PLoS One*, 9(5), e97835 (2014).
54. Bao, G., Suresh, S., Cell and molecular mechanics of biological materials. *Nat Mater.*, 2, 715–25 (2003).
55. Place, E.S., Evans, N.D., Stevens, M.M., Complexity in biomaterials for tissue engineering. *Nat Mater.*, 8, 457–470 (2009).